

A Case Report

Diagnostic & Therapeutic approach to Oral Pyogenic Granuloma

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Abstract

One type of inflammatory hyperplasia observed in the mouth cavity is pyogenic granuloma. The underlying irritating reasons that cause pyogenic granuloma include hormonal variables, severe injuries, and local irritation. In a clinical setting, it appears as a sessile, pedunculated, or smooth exophytic hemorrhagic base. Patients with this illness often experience discomfort, poor aesthetics, and occasionally difficulty chewing. A surgically treated case of pyogenic granuloma is presented in this research.

Introduction

A frequent benign vascular tumor that can affect people of all ages is called a pyogenic granuloma¹. In 1904, Hartzell first used the phrase "pyogenic granuloma." Hullihen's initial report of a pyogenic granuloma was published in 1844². Mucous membranes and skin can both be impacted. The most frequent cause of it is trauma. An inflammatory hyperplasia known as pyrogenic granuloma (PG) is characterized by nodular development in the oral mucosa that histologically resembles inflammatory fibrous granulation tissues³. Pyogenic granuloma is more common in the anterior than the posterior region and is more frequently observed in the maxilla than in the mandible [4]. It is known that gingiva is mostly affected by PG⁴. In addition to gingiva, the lips, tongue, buccal mucosa, and palate may be impacted. Most of the time, it is a solitary lesion with a vivid red or purplish coloring, and a hard or soft consistency (10–12)^{5,6}. The lesion ranges in size from a few millimeters to a few centimeters and bleeds readily at the slightest

stimulation.⁷ It can be smooth, granular, lobulated, pedunculated, sessile, ulcerated, necrotic, or not surface-related. It is defined by the nodular volumetric increase of the connective tissue.⁸ The anamnesis and the histology analysis are the primary factors that determine the differential diagnosis⁹. It is comparable to various mucosal lesions, including metastatic tumors, hemangiomas, basal cell carcinomas, leiomyomas, inflammatory fibroepithelial hyperplasia, giant cell granulomas, and hemangioendotheliomas¹⁰. The goal of treatment is to eliminate the contributing factor and do an excisional biopsy.

Case Presentation

The primary complaint of a 23-year-old female patient who went to the department of periodontology had an excruciating gum swelling in the upper left jaw region that had been causing her discomfort for the previous two to three months when

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eating. It was small at first and became more noticeable with time. One month before to coming into our outpatient department, she saw a doctor, who prescribed multivitamin and gum paint for topical use. Because of the bleeding, she had stopped brushing that area. No history of systemic illness was provided by the patient. There was no swelling that was observed on the left sided maxilla during the extraoral examination. A solitary left submandibular lymph node was palpable at approximately 0.6x0.4 cm, roughly oval, soft, mobile, and non-tender. An intraoral examination of Figure 1 showed a well-defined sessile growth involving marginal and attached gingiva in the left maxillary LI-canine-premolar region, extending from the palatal and buccal region. It was oval in shape, roughly 4.4 by 3 cm, and had a reddish-pink tint. There were no visible ulcerations, and the surface was smooth.

FIGURE 1: Pre-operative view of pyogenic granuloma

It was tender on palpation with a soft consistency. Poor oral hygiene and calculus were present. There were no indications of mobility in the teeth surrounding the lesion. With the exception of radiological abnormalities displaying periodontal expansion, as depicted in Figure 2. A typical hemogram was discovered to be anticipated. The diagnosis of PG was made. Peripheral giant cell granuloma and peripheral ossifying fibroma were included in the differential diagnosis. The goal of periodontal therapy has traditionally been to mechanically remove infectious microorganisms in order to decrease bacterial infection. As a result, a thorough oral prophylactic regimen was adhered to, and the clinical and radiological data were used to prepare the patient for surgery. Following the end of phase I therapy, a follow-up was conducted. As a

result, the periodontal examination showed minor gingival inflammation based on a gingival index score of <1 by Loe and Silness in 1963 and an excellent plaque index score of <1 by Silness and Loe in 1964. As a result, it was agreed to move forward with the surgical procedure.

FIGURE 2: Radiographic changes of the pyogenic granuloma with respect to the affected area

To remove the lesion, a conventional scalpel-based surgical approach was selected. The purpose of the blood examinations was to rule out hemoglobin, bleeding time, and clotting time ranges. The blood investigation's findings stayed within acceptable bounds. Prior to the surgical treatment, the patient provided written and signed informed permission. An area was anesthetized with a solution of 2% lignocaine with 1:200000 adrenaline under all aseptic precautions. The lesion was then demarcated. A circumferential full-thickness incision was given. The incision extended from the distal aspect of the canine (maxillary left) to the mesial part of the first molar (maxillary left) region.

FIGURE 3: Surgical excision is done by the scalpel of the pyogenic

granuloma

It had a delicate consistency and was palpably sensitive. There was calculus and poor oral hygiene. There were no evidence of movement in the teeth surrounding the lesion. As seen in Figure 2, there were no obvious abnormalities on radiographs other than minor alveolar bone loss in the development zone and periodontal widening with roots of 12,13 and 14. It was found that an average hemogram was anticipated. PG was identified as the cause. The differential diagnosis includes peripheral ossifying fibroma and peripheral giant cell granuloma. The objective of periodontal therapy has traditionally been to mechanically remove infectious microorganisms in order to decrease bacterial infection. As a result, a thorough oral prophylactic regimen was adhered to, and the clinical and radiological data were used to prepare the patient for surgery. Following the end of phase I therapy, a follow-up was conducted. As a result, the periodontal examination showed minor gingival inflammation based on a gingival index score of <1 by Loe and Silness in 1963 and an excellent plaque index score of <1 by Silness and Loe in 1964. As a result, it was agreed to move forward with the surgical procedure.

FIGURE 4: Recall examination after seven days revealed complete healing of the pyogenic granuloma

In order to differentiate similar characteristics, histopathological criteria are required. Consequently, histopathology analyses were performed. A single tissue segment covering epithelium and underlying connective tissue stroma was found upon histopathological examination. The thickness of the para-keratinized stratified squamous epithelium that overlaid it varied in certain areas. There was a significant chronic

inflammatory cell infiltration, primarily of lymphocytes, in the surrounding connective tissue stroma. Red blood cells that were both intravasated and extravasated were also visible in a large number of thin, dilated blood vessels. In some areas, the connective tissue stroma had a myxoid appearance. As seen in Figure 5, all of these low power view findings were validated in high power, and the features were suggestive of PG. Thus the definitive diagnosis of PG was made on the basis of a histology report.

FIGURE 5: Histologic findings of pyogenic granuloma

Treatment

Surgical excision is the treatment for pyogenic granulomas. By using a nonsurgical method, irritating factors are debrided while under local anesthesia, and rigorous oral hygiene guidelines are adhered to. If the lesion is not encapsulated, it will recur. When surgically excising PG, it is advised to cure the underlying tissue.^{8,9}

Discussion

Hormonal variables, acute damage, and low-grade local irritation are determined to be the common components that contribute to post-glaucoma. They usually show up following trauma. A significant number of the patients may have had a contributing component in their poor oral hygiene. Due to the vascular effects of female hormones, they are most prevalent in the second decade of life. Due to calculus or foreign material collection within the gingival crevice, they are most frequently detected in the gingiva, accounting for 75% of all instances. The tongue and buccal mucosa are the next most prevalent locations. In the case study, there was a single, reddish-pink, oval, sessile growth that measured about 4.4 by 3 cm. It involved

the gingival border and attachment, and it was soft and painful. It exists in both lobular and non-lobular histological types. A greater number of blood vessels that are proliferating and exhibiting little to no specific modifications indicate a lobular shape. In addition, a non-lobular shape is indicated by alignment with endothelial cells and the presence of dilated capillary channels¹³. "Peripheral giant cell granuloma, peripheral ossifying fibroma, peripheral fibroma, Kaposi's sarcoma, angiosarcoma, metastatic carcinoma, non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, and hemangioma" should be included in relation to the differential diagnosis¹⁴. Because many other intraoral angiomatous lesions have a similar clinical appearance, diagnosing PG can often be difficult. Consequently, a thorough clinical examination is required. Differentiation is based on clinical and histological traits, which helps with treatment planning and, as a result, improves prognosis. To reduce the likelihood of recurrence, PG treatment comprises removing all etiological factors and executing a complete surgical excision. A stainless-steel knife is typically used for incisional surgeries¹⁵. Asnaashari et al., reported that the lesion recurrence rate following the conventional method was 16%. Since the lesion in our patient had a sessile basis and a history of recurrent recurrence, the standard scalpel method was recommended. To stop the lesion from returning, the entire underlying soft tissue was removed during the excision¹⁶. Throughout the maintenance procedure, no recurrence was seen. The majority of PGs that develop during pregnancy go away after delivery. It is advised to treat the lesion in the second trimester of pregnancy if it is large or causes bleeding, and to continue monitoring it after delivery. The preferred therapies include also diode or CO₂, cryosurgery, laser resection, flashlamp-pumped pulsed dye laser, intralesional injection of corticosteroids or sclerosing agents, and nitrogen cryosurgery¹⁴.

Conclusion

This case discusses the lesion's clinical and histological characteristics and notes that, despite being often used, the name "pyogenic granuloma" is incorrect because it is not pus-associated and is histologically angiomatous rather than granulomatous. Excision surgery will remain the

preferred treatment option despite the availability of new choices because it can be finished in a single session with normal surgical instruments, whereas other treatments require numerous appointments, specialist staff training, and costly equipment. Additionally, it is simple to use in standard clinical practice, and following surgical excision, recurrence is uncommon. This case indicates entirety, satisfactory healing following the removal of the pyogenic granuloma using a normal scalpel technique. There is no formation of scar tissue, pain, or discomfort, and the problems associated with mastication are relieved, meeting the patient's functional and aesthetic needs.

References

1. Jafarzadeh H, Sanatkhan M, Mohtasham N. Oral pyogenic granuloma: a review. *J Oral Sci* 2006;48(4):167-175.
2. Hartzell MB: Granuloma pyogenicus. *J Cutan Dis*. 1904, 22:520-3.
3. Kurian, Dr. Bobby, Dr. Sasirekha, Dr. Ebenezer. "Pyogenic Granuloma- a Case Report and Review." *International Journal of Dental Sciences and Research* 2.3 2014: 66-68.
4. Ganesan A, Kumar NG, Azariah E, Asokan GS. Oral pyogenic granuloma: A case report and a comprehensive review. *SRM J Res Dent Sci* 2015;6:257-60
5. Saikhedkar R, Shrivastava S, Melkundi M, Viswanathan V. Pyogenic granuloma--a case report. *International Journal of Dental Clinics*. 2011 Jul 1;3(3):87-9.
6. Giblin AV, Clover AJ, Athanassopoulos A, Budny PG. Pyogenic granuloma - the quest for optimum treatment: audit of treatment of 408 cases. *J Plast Reconstr Aesthet Surg*. 2007;60:1030-5.
7. Al-Khateeb T, Ababneh K. Oral pyogenic granuloma in Jordanians: a retrospective analysis of 108 cases. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg*. 2003;61:1285-8.
8. Kamal R, Dahiya P, Puri A. Oral pyogenic granuloma: various concepts of etiopathogenesis. *J Oral Maxillofac Pathol* 2012;16(1):79.
9. Frumkin N, Nashef R, Shapira L, Wilensky A. Nonsurgical treatment of recurrent gingival pyogenic granuloma: a case report. *Quintessence Int* 2015;46(6):539-544.
10. Shenoy SS, Dinkar AD. Pyogenic granuloma associated with bone loss in an eight year old child: A case report. *J Indian Soc Pedod Prev Dent*. 2006;24:201-3.
11. Loe H, Sillness J. The gingival index and the retention index system. *J Periodontol*. 1963;38-44
12. Sillness J, Loe H. The Plaque index and the retention index system. *J Periodontol*. 1964;4(1):38-44
13. Asnaashari M, Zadsirjan S Application of laser in oral surgery. *J Lasers Med Sci*. 2014, 5:97-107.
14. Buchner A, Calderon S, Ramon Y Localized hyperplastic lesions of the gingiva: a clinicopathological study of 302 lesions. *J Periodontol*. 1977, 48:101-4.
15. Abdulai AE, Nuamah IK, Baddoo H, Gyasi RK Oral pyogenic granuloma in Ghanaians: a review of cases. *Int J Med Biomed Res*. 2013, 2:173-8.
16. Asnaashari M, Bigom-Taheri J, Mehdiipoor M, Bakhshi M, Azari-Marhabi S Posthaste outgrow of lip pyogenic granuloma after diode laser removal. *J Lasers Med Sci*. 2014, 5:92-5.2023